

CANDIDATE LANDING SITES AT THE LUNAR SOUTH POLE FOR SOLAR-POWERED ROVER OPERATIONS. J. Flahaut^{1*}, S. AlMaeni², M. AlZaabi², H. AlMarzooqi², K. Badri², H. AlMatroushi² and the ELM Science Collaboration.

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Introduction : Over the past decades, increasing evidence has accumulated for the presence of near-surface volatiles at the lunar poles [e.g., 1-4]. Lunar water ice and other cold-trapped volatiles are of high scientific interest, both as potential archives of Solar System evolution and as key resources for future exploration [e.g., 4-5]. In addition, the opportunity to investigate the geology of the South Pole-Aitken (SPA) basin has motivated space agencies worldwide to target the lunar south pole with upcoming missions.

The south polar region is characterized by rough topography due to its location on the rim of the SPA basin and the superposition of large impact craters [6-7]. Combined with the Moon's small axial inclination, this rugged terrain leads to extreme illumination conditions [e.g., 8-9]. Deep craters that never receive direct sunlight form permanently shadowed regions (PSRs), which provide favorable environments for the long-term cold trapping of volatiles [10]. In contrast, most polar surfaces are illuminated for less than 50% of the time, posing significant challenges for solar-powered exploration systems that must continuously manage power availability. Nevertheless, limited areas experiencing near-persistent illumination (exceeding ~80% on average over a lunar day) have been identified near the rims of Shackleton, de Gerlache, and Nobile craters, along the connecting ridge between Shackleton and de Gerlache, and on the crest of the Malapert Massif [9].

The present paper investigates candidate landing sites that would allow a 30+ days rover mission at the lunar south pole with a "chase-the-light" operational scenario. After landing ellipse selection, a time-dependent traverse was designed at a selected test site located on the connecting ridge between the Shackleton and de Gerlache craters. Although this work was primarily conducted as a feasibility study for the MBRSC Rashid 3 rover mission (for which the carrier, launch date, and landing site are still to be determined [11]), our results allow us to discuss how polar illumination conditions strongly influence landing site selection, surface operations, and the accessibility of volatile-rich regions.

Dataset and methods : All available datasets were combined within a Geographic Information System (GIS), following approaches described in [3, 12, 13]. The data collection includes LROC WAC

and NAC polar mosaics; LOLA digital elevation models and derived slope maps at resolutions ranging from 5 to 20 m/px; LOLA products including average illumination, Earth visibility, and PSR distribution [9]; Diviner bolometric temperature maps (average, minimum, and maximum) and predicted ice stability depth [10], and USGS geological maps.

The QuickMap TerrainShadows interface (2D cartographic mode, QTS-2D) [14] was further used to generate hourly and daily illumination maps over a 2.5×2.5 km area centered on the selected, test landing ellipse, at a spatial resolution of 5 m/px. Illumination was modeled over a 63-day test period arbitrarily set from October 1 to December 1, 2028. Hourly and daily maps were stacked to construct three-dimensional data cubes, which were then summed to estimate the total illumination received over the selected time period. In addition, the subsolar point, as well as Sun azimuth and elevation, were documented at each waypoint along the designed traverse.

Results : Landing ellipse selection. Starting from the 56 well-illuminated south polar locations identified in [9], we computed zonal statistics of surface slope for circular landing ellipses with diameters of 100 m, 200 m, 1 km, and 2 km, centered on the permanently illuminated points. Following the approach adopted for the Rashid 1 rover, a candidate landing ellipse was considered suitable if its average slope was below 10° , with at least 95% of the ellipse surface area complying with this criterion [13].

We show that for ellipses larger than 1 km in diameter, the fraction of compliant pixels within the ellipse drops below 52%. For a 200 m diameter ellipse, the most favorable case is located between the Shackleton and Faustini craters, yet yields only 88% compliant pixels, based on slope values derived from the 10 m/px LOLA DEM. These results indicate that exploration of areas experiencing near-persistent illumination would require very high-precision landing capabilities, with an accuracy better than 100 m.

When considering a 100 m diameter ellipse, all locations satisfying the slope criteria are situated on the connecting ridge between the Shackleton and de Gerlache craters, as well as along the rim of de Gerlache. Among these, Ellipse #36, centered at -89.44° , -137.25° , in the vicinity of the Artemis III candidate site 001, was selected as a test site for the mission design study (Fig. 1).

Candidate traverse path. All boulders and PSRs, which are considered as potential science targets, were mapped within a 10×10 km area centered on the selected landing ellipse. Using the LOLA DEM and derived slope maps at 5 m/px resolution, a least-cost path algorithm was applied to identify which targets were accessible from the landing site under a maximum slope constraint of 15° . Areas of near-permanent illumination were also identified as potential safe, “rest and recharge” locations. QTS-2D simulations show that the illuminated areas migrate anticlockwise around the landing ellipse over the course of a lunar day. This behavior was therefore adopted as a guiding constraint for the design of the reference traverse.

Selected science stations and safe illumination points were defined as waypoints and connected using the shortest traversable paths while maintaining slopes below 15° . Illumination duration and Sun azimuth were extracted at each waypoint to determine the time available for traversing between successive points, assuming that rover operations are not possible in darkness (except for limited short-duration excursions into PSRs for scientific measurements), and that the rover preferentially maintains the Sun on either its left or right side.

The final proposed traverse visits to three PSRs and one boulder field (Fig. 1). The total distance traveled from point 0 (landing site, left on October 17th, 2028) to point 9 (boulder field, reached on November 10th, 2028) is 395 m, with an average elevation of 1954 ± 4 m and a mean slope of 4.6° . The scenario includes 11 non-driving days spent at science stations #2, #3, #5, and #9.

Discussion : The present work highlights the strong constraints imposed by the topography of the lunar south pole, where well-illuminated areas are largely restricted to narrow crater rims and topographic crests, thereby requiring high-precision landing capabilities. Among these locations, we identify the most favorable 100 m diameter landing ellipse, in terms of combined illumination and slope criteria, on the connecting ridge between the Shackleton and de Gerlache craters.

Our results further demonstrate the feasibility of a 30-day rover mission operating under a “chase-the-

light” strategy, capable of visiting both micro-scale permanently shadowed regions (micro-PSRs) and boulder fields, with a mean driving distance of approximately 25 m per Earth day. However, large subsurface ice deposits inferred from orbital observations remain largely inaccessible from highly illuminated terrains. As a result, in situ investigations of lunar volatiles at the south pole are likely to remain limited to enigmatic micro-scale PSRs, where water ice may persist at depth despite the surrounding illuminated environment.

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References: [1] Colaprete A. et al. (2010) *Science*, 330, 463-468. [2] Hayne P.O. et al. (2015) *Icarus*, 255, 58-69. [3] Flahaut J. et al. (2020) *PSS*, 180, 104750. [4] Anand M. et al. (2014) *Phil. Trans. R. Soc., A* 372. [5] Flahaut J. et al. (2023) *npj microgravity*, 9(1), 50. [6] Wilhelms D.E. et al. (1979) *US Geological Survey*. [7] Spudis P. D. et al. (2008), *GRL*, 35(14). [8] Bussey D.B.J. et al. (1999) *GRL*, 9, 1187-1190. [9] Mazarico, E. et al. (2011) *Icarus*, 211. [10] Paige, D. et al. (2010) *Science*, 330. [11] AlMatroushi H. et al. (2026) *this meeting*. [12] Losekamm M. et al. (2022) *Planet. Sci. J.*, 3 229. [13] Flahaut J. et al. (2024) *Space Sci. Rev.*, 220, 53. [14] ACT, <https://lunar.quickmap.io/>.

Figure 1: Test traverse on the connecting ridge between de Gerlache and Shackleton craters, near the lunar south pole. Left : Background map is the average Sun visibility map (i.e., fraction of time the surface is illuminated, from black to white) of Mazarico et al. (2011), 100m diameter candidate landing ellipses are displayed in green; Right : Background map is the LOLA polar digital elevation model at 5 m/px overlain in transparency over the LROC NAC data, the proposed traverse is shown in red and connects features of interest while constantly chasing the sunlight as lunar time of the day evolves.

